

MOTIVATIONS AND THEIR EFFECT ON JOB SATISFACTION AN APPLIED STUDY ON EMPLOYEES OF JORDANIAN COMMERCIAL BANKS

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Abstract

This study aimed at identifying the impact of financial and moral incentives, based on an applied study on the Jordanian commercial banks. The researcher used the analytical descriptive approach to demonstrate the concepts relating to the study topic, analyze them and come up with the results. The study sample was selected randomly and consisted of (130) individuals working in the departments of human resources in the Jordanian commercial banks. In order to achieve the study objectives, a questionnaire was developed to collect data from the study sample individuals. The researcher collected the data, analyzed them and tested the hypotheses by using the Statistical Package of Social Sciences (SPSS). The results revealed that the level of evaluating the workers (the study sample) in banks with regard to financial and moral incentives was high. The results also revealed that the level of evaluating the workers (the study sample) in banks with regard to employees' satisfaction was high. The results showed that there is a statistically significant impact for financial and moral incentives on employee's satisfaction. In the light of the results, the study concluded with a number of recommendations for banks and researchers to make advantage of incentives to increase employee's satisfaction, and thus increase productivity.

Key words: financial and moral incentives, employee's satisfaction.

Introduction:

During the last few years and up to now, the world has witnessed several changes in the various domains of contemporary life, where these changes affected all the political, social and economic organizations in the world's countries regardless the degree of their progress and development. Those variables affected the structure of values and the nature of societal relationships in many countries across the world to the extent that justified the saying which started "now, we live in a new world" that totally differs from the previous one, which extended over centuries and up to the early 1980s. Gure, Naima Abdullahi (2010), Al Jishi, Hala Abdulhadi (2009).

In the light of those changes, there has been more interest in the human resources in the contemporary organizations; indeed, administration realized the important role played by those resources in terms of their contribution to achieving the objectives of the organization. Furthermore, there has been more prevalence in using the concepts of strategic administration in business organizations as well as other organizations which aim at achieving certain results and objectives by using the technical, financial and human resources Alfandi, Ashraf Mohammad. (2014).

It can be said that the first emergence of human resources was in the period of industrial revolution which, in turn, led to several causes that manifested the importance of this element in all types of activities, whether they were related to labor (productivity) or anything else. The

industrial revolution confirmed the importance of establishing an administrative department of human resources that is concerned with the affairs of managing the various types of institutions, in that it promotes individuals and raises their morale which, in turn, increases the level of productivity Kaneez Fatima Mamdani, (2016), Jabeen, Maimona (2011).

Accordingly, we may conclude the importance of this element in the process of production, where no employer can manage his work without the existence of human resources in the organization despite the existence of machines. In this study, the researcher addressed the impact of motivation on achieving job satisfaction among the workers in the commercial banks working in Jordan.

The study problem:

Organizations are interested in providing a work force that is appropriate, sufficient and well-qualified to do the tasks delegated to them successfully and achieve the objectives of the organization. In order to do so, organizations look for accurate and objective practical methods to attract employees and then train them according to the nature and basic requirements of work, so that the employees will be qualified to perform the required tasks. The efficiency in doing work depends on basic pillars, including the desire to work and succeed in it. Indeed, this can be achieved by providing the various types of motivations to employees.

The research importance:

- 1- The reality of the Jordanian environment, where organizations face internal and external stressors and challenges- the research acquired its importance from the connection between these challenges and the Jordanian environment.
- 2- The research contributes to shedding more light on a vital and important topic that represents a basic element in the success of organizations.
- 3- The role played by the various types of motivations (financial, moral) in promoting the level of job satisfaction.
- 4- The recommendations introduced by the researcher and the extent to which they are useful in the practical reality.

The research objectives:

This research aims to achieving the following:

- 1- Identifying the impact of financial incentives on achieving job satisfaction among the employees in the Jordanian commercial banks.
- 2- Identifying the types of moral motivations and their role in achieving job satisfaction among the employees in the Jordanian commercial banks.
- 3- Identifying the types of moral and financial motivations granted to the employees in the Jordanian commercial banks.

The theoretical framework:

(Daniel, 2019) conducted a study entitled "The EffectsofIncentivesonEmployeesproductivity". The study aimed at identifying the relationship between incentives and the employee's productivity in organizations as well as analyzing the relationship between incentives and the employee's productivity in organizations in Nigeria. In order to achieve the study objectives, a questionnaire was developed based on the study objectives. The results showed that there is a positive correlation relationship between incentives and productivity. Besides the financial incentives, there is another basic factor that motivates employees, which is involving them in the process which aims to achieve the organizational effectiveness, which cannot b achieved without their cooperation. The study recommended the necessity of establishing a unit that investigates the issues related to incentives which could promote productivity.

(Novianty, et al, 2018) conducted a study which aimed at identifying the impact of financial incentives on the productivity of employees, where the financial incentives refer to a reward that is given to the employee to motivate him/ her to perform better in the future. The study used the analytical approach, and the questionnaires were used based on a differential rating. The study population consisted of (43) employees. The results revealed that financial incentives have a positive impact on motivating employees.

(Chepkemoi, 2018) conducted a study which aimed at identifying the impact of incentives on the performance of employees serving the forests in Kenya. The study was based on the theory of field change and Chang's theory of development. The study used the descriptive approach with its survey image. The results revealed that incentives are necessary in organizational performance. The study recommended the necessity of urging the Kenyan forest services and the other public institutions to re-engineer their processes systems in order to improve customer services, in addition to introducing new values of teamwork and cooperation in order to reduce employee turnover which, in turn,improvesthe organizational image.

(Rina Novianty, 2018) conducted a study which aimed at improving the personal performance of employees. The study sample consisted of (43) employees. The results revealed that the programs of financial incentives promote changes in motivation to change work patterns and motivate employees to work. The study recommended the necessity of conducting further studies related to the policies of motivating employees and improving the performance of employees.

(AL-Omari, et al, 2017) conducted a study which aimed at identifying the impact of incentives on the performance of employees in the public sector. The results revealed that guided insensitive have a positive impact on individuals, in terms of performing work in the organization. The results weren't affected by the nature of the investigated entity whether as a school or other public institution. The results confirmed the impact of competition structure for the incentives system, where those performing better would receive more incentives. There was no impact for the study approach, whether it was a laboratory or field study.

The study approach:

In the light of the study results and nature, the study used the analytical descriptive approach which is based on investigating the reality of the phenomenon, describes it accurately and demonstrates its characteristics. This approach also describes the phenomenon quantitatively, where it describes the targeted phenomenon with numbers and demonstrates its size and the extent to which it is related to other phenomena. In addition to describing reality, this approach comes up with conclusions that contribute to understanding and developing the reality that was monitored Sekaran, U. & Bougie, R. (2013).

The study population:

The population refers to all the components of a certain phenomenon which constitute the topic of the study problem. The population of this study consisted of a group of employees in the department of human resources and other departments that are directly related to that, with a total of (130) individuals from different sections in the department of human resources in banks and other departments. The study sample consisted of (70) individuals selected from the targeted study population.

The study instrument:

Based on the nature of the collected data, the study approach, the allotted time and the available financial potentials, the researcher decided to use the questionnaire as the study instrument. Therefore, the researcher developed a questionnaire based on the studies that addressed motivation and job satisfaction.

The reliability of the study instrument:

Cronbach alpha coefficient was calculated in order to verify the internal consistency of the questionnaire's items, where its value was (89%). We can notice that the values of the reliability coefficients for the dependant and independent variables were high, and acceptable for the purposes of performing the statistical analysis for the study data.

Answering the study questions:

In order to answer the study questions, the researcher calculated the means and standard deviations for the perceptions of the study individuals relating to the dependent and independent variables. The results are illustrated in table (1).

Table 1: The means and standard deviation for the responses of the study sample individuals

Number	Dimension	Mean	SD	Level of item
1	Financial incentives	3.85	0.65	High
2	Moral incentives	3.80	0.69	High
Dependent variable " employee's job satisfaction"		3.75	0.70	High

Table (1) revealed that the means and standard deviations for the variables of "financial incentives" and "employee's job satisfaction" were relatively high.

The results showed that the total mean for the indicators of the variable of financial incentives was (3.67). The dimension of financial incentives was in the first place with a mean of (3.85), followed by the dimension of moral incentives with a mean of (3.80).

As for the means and standard deviations for the dependant variable "employee's job satisfaction", it was with a high degree with a total mean of (3.76).

Testing the study hypothesis:

There is no statistically significant impact at ($\alpha=0.05$) between the financial and moral incentives and the satisfaction of employees working in the Jordanian commercial banks.

In this part, the researcher tests the study hypothesis that was cited based on the study problem and questions using the appropriate statistical method as follows:

The multiple regression analysis test was performed to identify the impact of the dimensions of independent variables (administrative information systems with their indicators and the variable of knowledge administration with its indicators) on excellence culture. Table (2) shows the results.

Table 2: The analysis of multiple regression for the impact of financial and moral incentives on the satisfaction of employees

Variable	R	*correlation significance	R ²	β	Calculated f-value	*F significance
The dimensions of financial and moral incentives on the satisfaction of employees	0.881	0.000	0.671	0.089	63.148	0.000

* Statistically significant at ($\alpha=0.05$)

Table (2) revealed the following:

- 1- The significance of the model of multiple regression based on the significance of (f-value) calculated at a significance level of (0.000), which is less than ($\alpha=0.05$). This means that the regression model is highly valid to measure the impact of incentives on employee's satisfaction.
- 2- There is a statistically significant positive relationship at (0.05) between incentives and the satisfaction of employees, since the significance value was less than ($\alpha=0.05$).
- 3- The determination coefficient (R²) was (0.671), which means that the variable of incentives accounts for (67%) of Variance in the changes for the variable of employee's satisfaction, whereas the rest of the percentage (33%) is attributed to other variables not included in the regression model.

4- The value of the standard coefficient (BETA) was (0.089); this refers to the impact value for the variable of incentives on employee's satisfaction.

Discussing the study results:

1- The results revealed that the means for the perceptions of the employees (the study sample) in the Jordanian commercial banks concerning the dimensions of financial incentives and moral incentives were high, where the total mean for the financial and moral incentives was (3.82).

2- The results revealed that the means for the perceptions of the employees (the study sample) in the Jordanian commercial banks concerning the satisfaction of employees were high, where the total mean for the financial and moral incentives was (3.75).

3- The results showed that the financial and moral incentives are correlated with the dependent variable (employee's satisfaction) with a value of (0.881), which is considered as a strong positive correlation. We can also notice that the determination coefficient was (0.671), which means that (67.1%) of changes are attributed to moral and financial incentives, whereas the rest of the percentage (33%) is attributed to other variables not included in the regression model. We also noticed that the calculated (f-value) was (63.148), which is statistically significant at ($\alpha=0.05$), which means that the moral and financial incentives have a significant impact on the satisfaction of employees. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis, stating that there is no statistically significant impact at ($\alpha=0.05$) between the financial and moral incentives and the satisfaction of employees working in the Jordanian commercial banks.

Recommendations:

Based on the results, the study recommended the following:

1- The study recommends the necessity of urging other organizations to be aware of the concept of financial incentives due to its benefits on the satisfaction of employees in the Jordanian commercial banks.

2- The study recommends the necessity of urging other organizations to be aware of the concept of moral incentives due to its benefits on the satisfaction of employees in the Jordanian commercial banks.

3- The necessity of urging the various institutions to modify and activate the systems of moral incentives with their various types due to their effect on job performance of employees in these institutions.

4- The necessity of encouraging the investigated organizations to cite the laws and regulations that promote the practices of motivations and incentives in these organizations.

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